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Assessing the Avifauna, Odonata, and Lepidoptera of Kirala Kele Sanctuary, Wet Zone of Sri Lanka and Conservation Implications

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ABSTRACT

The Kirala Kele Sanctuary in the Matara District, Sri Lanka, covers approximately 1800 hectares of diverse wetland ecosystems that range from marshlands to riparian zones, paddy fields, and woodlands. This study quantifies the biodiversity of avifauna, butterflies, and odonates across four different habitat types during 12 replicate line transect surveys from March 2022 to July 2023, representing multiple climatic seasons. Field observations recorded 104 bird species, which represent 20% of Sri Lanka's avian diversity, 58 species of butterflies, which is 23.5% of the country's total, and 27 odonate species, which represent 20.6% of the total of the island. Key diversity metrics, such as Shannon-Wiener (H'), Simpson's ($1/D$), and evenness indices (E), showed habitat-specific patterns in biodiversity. Bird diversity was highest in transect 02 which represents the paddy-water catchment area, with an H' value of 3.42, and was attributed to a mix of aquatic and terrestrial resources. The highest diversity of butterflies ($H' = 1.85$), and odonates ($H' = 1.99$) were performed by transect 01 (marshy land ecosystem), probably because of its freshwater availability and dense aquatic vegetation. The endemism and conservation status of the area were represented by five endemic bird species, including *Psilopogon rubricapillus*, *Megalaima flavifrons*, *Dinopium psarodes*, *Chrysocolaptes stricklandi*, and *Loriculus*

beryllinus one endemic butterfly species, *Jamides lacteata*, and one endemic odonate species, *Pseudagrion rubriceps ceylonicum*. Furthermore, 11 threatened species across the three faunal taxonomic groups emphasize the critical need for conservation in the area. Other conservation challenges and threats identified were habitat degradation, alien invasive species, and anthropogenic pressures like agricultural encroachment and pollution. This makes attention to the implementation of sustainable agriculture practices and the involvement of the local communities in conservation matters. These findings form a useful baseline for biodiversity monitoring and stress the sanctuary's role in providing a vital refuge for wetland species. By highlighting the Kirala Kele Sanctuary's ecosystem heterogeneity and its significance for both biodiversity and livelihoods, this research advocates for integrated conservation strategies that balance ecological sustainability with local community needs. These insights are vital for informed decision-making and long-term management of wetland ecosystems in Sri Lanka.

Keywords: Biodiversity, Conservation, Diversity indices, Kirala Kele, Wetlands

1. INTRODUCTION

Wetlands rank among the most threatened ecosystems worldwide (Mitsch et al. 2009) and are globally recognized for their enormous ecological value. Wetlands play a vital role in maintaining and balancing biodiversity by providing habitats for a vital range of flora and fauna while providing various ecological services such as flood mitigation, water purification, livelihood options for human beings (Qiu et al. 2024; Mano et al., 2022; Eben et al., 2014). Different types of habitats can be observed in wetlands such as riparian habitats, swamps, ponds and lakes, and mangrove vegetation, etc. This habitat heterogeneity could be an important determinant of high diversity in wetlands. These different habitat types are utilized by many species of fauna for variety of functions.

Sri Lanka offers a home for a unique diversity of birds, butterflies, and odonates including 522, 247, and 129 species respectively (The National Red List 2021; Sumanapala 2017; Van der Poorten & Van der Poorten 2016). Different ecoregions and ecosystems in Sri Lanka offer habitats not only for endemic, native, and migratory species but also act as significant breeding grounds, and feeding grounds for many species due to ecological diversity. The conservation of such ecosystems is crucial to maintaining rich biodiversity and balanced ecology in respective regions. The wet zone and intermediate zone of the island is home to the richest tropical forests in the country, characterized by high, multi-layered canopies, along with lowland marsh wetlands. However, this landscape has recently been extensively cleared for human habitation, livelihoods, and agriculture, and especially for export-oriented rubber, coconut, and lowland plantations (Perera & Suranjan Fernando 2024).

The “Kirala Kele” sanctuary is a marshy wetland system, a well-known agricultural and recreational area located in the Matara District, in Southern region of Sri Lanka neighboring the Nilwala river (J Fernando & Mohd Shariff 2017). The sanctuary is a main wetland ecosystem in the region which provides shelter for many fauna and flora species. The area supports a significant number of flora including “Nelum” (*Nelumbo nucifera*), “Olu” (*Nymphaea pubescens*), “Manel” (*Nymphaea nouchali*), Kumudu (*Nymphodes indica*) “Belipatta” (*Hibiscus tiliaceus*), “Wel Kadurau” (*Cerbera manghas*), “Diyadanga” (*Dolichandrone spathacea*), and “Kerankoku” (*Acrosticum aureum*) are also found in the area.

The dominant species found in the marshland are “Olu” (*Nymphaea pubescens*), “Manel” (*Nymphaea nouchali*), “Kumudu” (*Nymphodes indica*), “Nalagas” (*Phragmites karka*), “Induru” (*Hanguana malayana*), “Hambu pan” (*Typha angustifolia*) and “Borupan” (*Eleocharis dulcis*) (De Silva Benthota et al. 2015). Many bird species including the Sri Lanka Hanging Parrot (*Loriculus beryllinus*), and Sri Lanka Swallow (*Cecropis hyperythra*), can be found feeding, nesting, and roosting in the area (Gunawardena et al. 2023). Previous records of butterflies and odonates in this sanctuary report a great diversity of invertebrates including Sri Lanka Orange-faced Sprite (*Pseudagrion rubriceps ceylonicum*), Variegated Flutterer (*Rhyothemis variegata variegata*) and Pied Parasol (*Neurothemis tullia tullia*) and butterflies such as Common Sailor (*Neptis hylas*), White Four Ring (*Ypthima ceylonica*), and Blue Glassy Tiger (*Ideopsis similis*) (Rathnayake et al. 2023; Priyadarshana et al. 2023).

This study aims to evaluate the diversity and distribution of avifauna, butterflies, and odonates in different habitats of the Kirala Kele sanctuary and analyze the implications for conservation with the data collected between March 2022 to July 2023. The study also will serve as baseline data for future conservation efforts through analyses of species richness, diversity indices, and evenness, as well as highlighting the importance of a variety of habitats in maintaining species diversity

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study area and habitats

Figure 1. Location of the study area in Kirala Kele Sanctuary in the Matara District in Sri Lanka.

The study was conducted at the Kirala Kele sanctuary (5°58' N 80°32' E) situated in the Matara District, Southern Province of Sri Lanka. The Kirala Kele sanctuary is located 3 km from Matara town, along the Matara-Hakmana and Matara-Akuressa roads. The Kirala Kele sanctuary consists of 1800 ha of an area with a dominating marshy wetland ecosystem. The district is located within the wet zone which experiences a mean annual temperature of 26.8 °C and a mean annual rainfall of 2147 mm (Liyanaige 2019). It comprises marshlands, irrigation canals, and mangrove habitats which are the most suitable habitats for wetland biodiversity.

The study area was divided into four different habitats based on ecosystems available and segmented (Figure 1).

The habitat types are described based on the general observations of the vegetation in the study area (Table 1). Transect 01 a Marshy ecosystem along with a waterway located close to the southern boundary of the sanctuary.

Transect 02 was a paddy-water catchment area ecosystem consisted of paddy fields located on the western side of the sanctuary. Several very attractive aquatic plants were found in the irrigation canals. Transect 03 consisted of riparian habitats with croplands which were found in the middle of the sanctuary. Scattered distributed Kirala (*Sonneratia caseolaris*) can be found at the edge of the irrigation canals. Transect 04 was the woodland-water-holding ecosystem surrounded by a marshy area.

Table 1. Habitat type within the study area based on observations.

Transect	Habitat Type
Transect 01 (T01)	Marshy land ecosystem
Transect 02 (T02)	Paddy- Water catchment area ecosystem
Transect 03 (T03)	Riparian habitats & Croplands
Transect 04 (T04)	Woodland-Water holding ecosystem

2. 2. Data collection

Four belt transects (Figure 1) in different habitats that are adjacent to the waterways were employed for 12 replicates (one replicate represents one morning session and one evening session) from mid-March 2022 to July 2023 covering all climatic seasons experienced by the area; northeast monsoon (January), short dry spell (February), first inter-monsoon (March-April), south-west monsoon (May-July), dry spell (July and August) and second inter-monsoon (September and October).

The survey of birds was conducted in the morning (0600 – 0900 h) and evening (1500 – 1800 h) for each study site along pre-established belt transects (200m × 20m). General weather conditions were noted during field visit. Birds were identified and enumerated while walking along the line transect at a ~10m/min speed. Maximum effort was taken to avoid double-counting as indicated by Sutherland, 2006. Birds were identified by visual observations and birdcalls using standard bird guides (Harrison & Worfolk 2011; Deepal Warakagoda et al. 2012; Kotagama & Fernando 1994).

Odonates and butterflies were surveyed along the same belt transects used for birds, with a change in width (200m × 5m) at each study site during warm and sunny conditions between 0800 – 1000 h and 1500 – 1700 h when odonates and butterflies are most active at a ~10m/min speed. Individuals were identified and recorded with the aid of standard field guides (Jayasinghe 2015; Sumanapala 2017; Jayasinghe et al. 2015).

If the organisms could not be identified in the field, photographs were taken using a DSLR camera (Nikon D7200) and were identified later. However, in cases where identification was difficult without a specimen in hand, live specimens were captured using a specially designed insect net and released to the same habitat.

Key biological and habitat parameters related to the behaviors (sitting, flight, feeding, mating, and oviposition) of all three taxa groups, specific microhabitat characteristics, and climate were also recorded. Further, opportunistic observations on all three faunal groups were recorded.

2. 3. Species inventory

A complete species inventory was prepared for the three faunal groups observed in the study area. The local conservation status (Least Concern, Near Threatened, Vulnerable, Endangered, or Critically Endangered) and the endemic or migratory nature of each species were documented following the National Red List 2012 (The National Red List 2012) of Sri Lanka and the National Red List Conservation Status of the Birds of Sri Lanka 2021 (The National Red List 2021).

2. 4. Diversity indices and habitat comparison

Species accumulation curves for each taxon were generated using the R statistical software package to estimate the number of species in each taxa group in the study area. Species richness (R), Shannon-Wiener diversity (H'), evenness (E), and Simpsons's diversity ($1/D$) were also calculated for each transect, and each taxa group using R statistical software particularly the features of the Vegan package, which is widely used in ecological research to analyze community ecology. Detailed instructions and functions for diversity indices are documented in (vegan documentation 2024) were employed and the following steps were carried out:

Species richness (S): Calculated using the `specnumber()` function, which counts the number of species in each sampling unit.

Shannon-Wiener Diversity (H'): This index was calculated using the `diversity()` function with the “shannon” option. The Shannon index responds to both species richness and the uniformity of species distribution in the community which is calculated as follows:

$$H' = -\sum p_i \ln p_i$$

where: $p_i = n_i/N$,

n_i = Total number of individuals belonging to i^{th} species,

N = Total number of individuals belonging to the sampled population

Simpson Diversity (1/D): The Simpson diversity index was calculated using the same Diversity() function with the Simpson option. The Simpson index emphasizes species dominance and is calculated as follows:

$$\frac{1}{D} = \frac{1}{\sum p_i^2}$$

where P_i = proportion of individuals belonging to each species

Evenness (E): The evenness was derived by dividing the Shannon index by the species richness to obtain a measure of how evenly individuals are distributed among species.

$$E = \frac{H'}{\ln S}$$

where: H' = Shannon – Weiner diversity index

S = Total number of species

3. RESULTS

3. 1. Inventory and composition of species in the Kirala Kele belong to selected faunal groups

The transect survey recorded 104 species of birds representing 46 families, 58 butterfly species belonging to five families, and 27 odonate species representing 3 families (Tables 2, 3 and 4). Species accumulation curves of all three faunal groups presented in Figure 2 reveal our effort has reached an asymptote suggesting that the survey has recorded most of the all three faunal groups in the study area.

Five species of birds were found to be endemic to Sri Lanka (4.8%) including *Psilopogon rubricapillus*, *Megalaima flavifrons*, *Dinopium psarodes*, *Chrysocolaptes stricklandi*, and *Loriculus beryllinus*. 18 migrant bird species were recorded across all the transects (17.1%) including *Acrocephalus dumetorum*, *Sarkidiornis melanotos*, *Falco amurensis*, *Hirundo rustica*, *Lanius cristatus*, *Sterna hirundo*, *Sternula albifrons*, *Chlidonias hybrida*, *Merops philippinus*, *Terpsiphone paradisi*, *Muscicapa dauurica*, *Muscicapa muttui*, *Phylloscopus nitidus*, *Phylloscopus magnirostris*, *Pitta brachyura*, *Tringa tetanus*, *Actitis hypoleucos*, *Tringa glareola* and *Platalea leucorodia*. Ardeidae was found to be the most dominant bird family with 12 species (11.42%), while families Acrocephalidae, Aegithinidae, Anhingidae, Charadriidae, Dicaeidae, Dicruridae, Falconidae, Jacanidae, Laniidae, Leiothrichidae, Motacillidae, Oriolidae, Pelecanidae, Phasianidae, Pittidae, Recurvirostridae and Sturnidae were the least dominant representing only one species (0.95%) each. Family Accipitridae, Alcedinidae, Cisticolidae, Columbidae, Muscicapidae, and Rallidae were reported as the second largest represented by four species (3.81%) each (Figure 3). Among the recorded species *Ixobrychus sinensis*, *Ploceus manyar*, and *Zapornia fusca* are listed as Endangered, while *Pernis ptilorhynchus* is listed as vulnerable in the National Red List - Conservation Status of the Birds of Sri Lanka (The National Red List 2021).

The results of the odonate study revealed that *Pseudagrion rubriceps ceylonicum* as the only endemic odonate species recorded. The most dominant odonate family recorded was

Libellulidae (70.37%) among all three recorded families while Platycnemididae (3.7%) was the least dominant family (Figure 4). Among the recorded odonate species *Ceriagrion coromandelianum*, *Trithemis festiva*, and *Onychargia atrocyana* are listed as the vulnerable species in the (The National Red List 2012).

Jamides lacteata was the only recorded endemic butterfly out of 58 recorded species. The Nymphalidae family (37.93%) was the most dominant butterfly family recorded during the study. Family Papilionidae (6.89%) was the least recorded family among all the recorded families.

Lycaenidae family (29.31%) was the second-highest recorded family, followed by Hesperiidae (29.31%) and Pieridae (8.62%) families (Figure 5). Among the recorded species, *Pelopidas conjuncta*, *Telicota bambusae*, *Jamides lacteata*, and *Ideopsis similis* are listed as vulnerable species (The National Red List 2012).

Table 2. Checklist of Birds in Kirala Kele Sanctuary (based on the current study).

No	Scientific name	Common name	SL Endemism / Migrant	National Conservation Status					Transect				
				L C	N T	V U	E N	C R	T01	T02	T03	T04	
Family: Accipitridae													
1	<i>Haliastur indus</i> (Boddaert, 1783)	Brahminy Kite		✓						+	+	+	+
2	<i>Spilornis cheela</i> (Latham, 1790)	Crested Serpent Eagle		✓						+		+	+
3	<i>Pernis ptilorhyncus</i> (Temminck, 1821)	Oriental Honey- buzzard				✓						+	
4	<i>Nisaetus cirrhatus</i> (Gmelin, 1788)	Crested hawk- Eagle		✓									+
Family: Acrocephalidae													
5	<i>Acrocephalus dumetorum</i> (Blyth, 1849)	Blyth's Reed Warbler	Migrant								+	+	
Family: Aegithinidae													
6	<i>Aegithina tiphia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Common Iora		✓								+	+
Family: Alcedinidae													
7	<i>Alcedo atthis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Common Kingfisher		✓						+	+	+	+

8	<i>Ceryle rudis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Pied Kingfisher		✓					+		+	
9	<i>Pelargopsis capensisensis</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	Stork-billed Kingfisher		✓					+	+	+	
10	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	White-throated Kingfisher		✓					+	+	+	+
Family: Anatidae												
11	<i>Dendrocygna javanica</i> (Horsfield, 1821)	Lesser Whistling Duck		✓					+	+	+	+
12	<i>Sarkidiornis melanotos</i> (Pennant, 1769)	Knob-billed Duck	Migrant									+
Family: Anhingidae												
13	<i>Anhinga melanogaster</i> (Pennant, 1769)	Oriental Darter		✓					+	+	+	+
Family: Apodidae												
14	<i>Apus affinis</i> (Gray, 1830)	House Swift		✓					+	+	+	+
15	<i>Cypsiurus balasiensis</i> (Gray, 1829)	Asian Palm-swift		✓					+	+	+	+
Family: Ardeidae												
16	<i>Ixobrychus flavicollis</i> (Latham, 1790)	Black Bittern		✓						+		+
17	<i>Nycticorax nycticorax</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Black-crowned Night-heron		✓						+	+	
18	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Cattle Egret		✓					+	+	+	+
19	<i>Ardea alba</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Great Egret		✓							+	
20	<i>Ardea cinerea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Grey Heron		✓						+	+	+
21	<i>Ardeola grayii</i> (Sykes, 1832)	Indian Pond-heron		✓					+	+	+	+
22	<i>Ardea intermedia</i> (Wagler, 1829)	Intermediate Egret		✓					+	+	+	+
23	<i>Egretta garzetta</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	Little Egret		✓					+	+	+	+
24	<i>Ardea purpurea</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	Purple Heron		✓					+	+	+	+
25	<i>Butorides striata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Striated Heron		✓								+

40	<i>Treron bicinctus</i> (Jerdon, 1840)	Orange-breasted Green Pigeon		✓						+		+		
41	<i>Spilopelia chinensis</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	Spotted Dove		✓						+	+	+	+	
Family: Corvidae														
42	<i>Corvus splendens</i> (Vieillot, 1817)	House Crow		✓						+	+	+	+	
43	<i>Corvus macrorhynchos</i> (Wagler, 1827)	Indian Jungle Crow		✓						+	+	+	+	
Family: Cuculidae														
44	<i>Eudynamys scolopaceus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Asian Koel		✓						+	+	+	+	
45	<i>Centropus sinensis</i> (Stephens, 1815)	Greater Coucal		✓						+		+	+	
Family: Dicaeidae														
46	<i>Dicaeum erythrorhynchos</i> (Latham, 1790)	Pale-billed Flowerpecker		✓						+	+	+	+	
Family: Dicruridae														
47	<i>Dicrurus caerulescens</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	White-bellied Drongo		✓						+	+	+	+	
Family: Estrildidae														
48	<i>Lonchura atricapilla</i> (Vieillot, 1807)	Black-headed Munia										+	+	+
49	<i>Lonchura punctulata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Scaly-breasted Munia		✓						+	+	+	+	
50	<i>Lonchura striata</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	White-rumped Munia		✓						+	+	+		
Family: Falconidae														
51	<i>Falco amurensis</i> (Radde, 1863)	Amur falcon	Migrant							+				
Family: Hirundinidae														
52	<i>Hirundo rustica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Barn Swallow	Migrant							+	+		+	
53	<i>Cecropis hyperythra</i> (Blyth, 1849)	Sri Lanka Swallow		✓						+	+	+	+	

Family: Jacanidae												
54	<i>Hydrophasianus chirurgus</i> (Scopoli, 1786)	Pheasant-tailed jacana		✓						+		+
Family: Laniidae												
55	<i>Lanius cristatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Brown shrike	Migrant							+		+
Family: Laridae												
56	<i>Sterna hirundo</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Common Tern	Migrant									+
57	<i>Sternula albifrons</i> (Pallas, 1764)	Little Tern	Migrant							+		
58	<i>Chlidonias hybrida</i> (Pallas, 1764)	Whiskered Tern	Migrant							+		+
Family: Leiotherichidae												
59	<i>Turdoides affinis</i> (Jerdon, 1845)	Yellow-billed Babbler		✓						+	+	+
Family: Megalaimidae												
60	<i>Psilopogon zeylanicus</i> (Gmelin, 1788)	Brown-headed Barbet								+	+	+
61	<i>Psilopogon rubricapillus</i> (Gmelin, 1788)	Sri Lanka Barbet	Endemic	✓						+	+	+
62	<i>Megalaima flavifrons</i> (Cuvier, 1816)	Sri Lanka Yellow-fronted Barbet	Endemic	✓						+		
Family: Meropidae												
63	<i>Merops philippinus</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	Blue-tailed bee-eater	Migrant							+	+	+
64	<i>Merops leschenaulti</i> (Vieillot, 1817)	Chestnut-headed Bee-eater			✓							+
65	<i>Merops orientalis</i> (Latham, 1802)	Little Green Bee-eater		✓						+	+	+
Family: Monarchidae												
66	<i>Terpsiphone paradisi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Asian Paradise Flycatcher	Migrant							+	+	+
Family: Motacillidae												
67	<i>Anthus rufulus</i> (Vieillot, 1818)	Paddyfield Pipit		✓						+	+	

Family: Muscicapidae												
68	<i>Muscicapa dauurica</i> (Asiatica, 1811)	Asian Brown Flycatcher	Migrant									+
69	<i>Muscicapa muttui</i> (Layard, 1854)	Brown-breasted Flycatcher	Migrant									+
70	<i>Saxicoloides fulicatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Indian Robin		✓								+
71	<i>Copsychus saularis</i> (Gray, 1840)	Oriental Magpie Robin		✓					+	+	+	+
Family: Nectariniidae												
72	<i>Cinnyris lotenius</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	Loten's Sunbird		✓					+		+	+
73	<i>Cinnyris asiatica</i> (Latham, 1790)	Purple Sunbird		✓					+	+	+	+
74	<i>Leptocoma zeylonica</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	Purple-rumped Sunbird		✓					+	+	+	+
Family: Oriolidae												
75	<i>Oriolus xanthornus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Black-hooded Oriole		✓					+	+	+	+
Family: Pelecanidae												
76	<i>Pelecanus philippensis</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	Spot-billed Pelican		✓						+		
Family: Phalacrocoracidae												
77	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Great Cormorant			✓						+	
78	<i>Phalacrocorax fuscicollis</i> (Stephens, 1826)	Indian Cormorant		✓					+	+		
79	<i>Microcarbo niger</i> (Vieillot, 1817)	Little Cormorant		✓					+	+	+	+
Family: Phasianidae												
80	<i>Pavo cristatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Indian Peafowl		✓					+	+	+	+
Family: Phylloscopidae												
81	<i>Phylloscopus nitidus</i> (Blyth, 1843)	Green warbler	Migrant									+

97	<i>Amaurornis phoenicurus</i> (Pennant, 1769)	White-breasted Waterhen		✓						+	+	+	+
Family: Recurvirostridae													
98	<i>Himantopus himantopus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Black-winged Stilt		✓							+	+	+
Family: Scolopacidae													
99	<i>Tringa totanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Common Redshank	Migrant								+		
100	<i>Actitis hypoleucos</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Common Sandpiper	Migrant								+		
101	<i>Tringa glareola</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Wood Sandpiper	Migrant								+		
Family: Sturnidae													
102	<i>Acridotheres tristis</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	Common Myna		✓						+	+	+	+
Family: Threskiornithidae													
103	<i>Threskiornis melanocephalus</i> (Latham, 1790)	Black-headed Ibis		✓							+	+	
104	<i>Platalea leucorodia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Eurasian Spoonbill	Migrant							+	+		

National Conservation Status (The National Red List, 2021): LC = Least Concern, NT = Near Threatened, VU = Vulnerable, EN = Endangered, CR = Critically Endangered.

Table 3. Checklist of Odonates in Kirala Kele Sanctuary (based on the current study).

No	Scientific name	Common name	SL Endemism / Migrant	National Conservation Status					Transect				
				L C	N T	V U	E N	C R	T01	T02	T03	T04	
Family: Coenagrionidae													
1	<i>Pseudagrion microcephalum</i> (Rambur, 1842)	Blue sprite		✓						+			
2	<i>Ischnura sengalensis</i> (Rambur, 1842)	Common Bluetail		✓								+	+

3	<i>Pseudagrion malabaricum</i> (Fraser, 1924)	Malabar Sprite		✓								+			+
4	<i>Pseudagrion rubriceps ceylonicum</i> (Drury, 1773)	Sri Lanka Orange-faced Sprite	Endemic	✓								+	+		+
5	<i>Ceriagrion coromandelianum</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	Painted Waxtail				✓						+	+	+	+
6	<i>Agriocnemis pygmaea</i> (Drury, 1773)	Wandering Wisp		✓								+	+	+	+
7	<i>Ceriagrion coromandelianum</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	Yellow Waxtail		✓								+	+	+	+
Family: Libellulidae															
8	<i>Brachythemis contaminata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	Asian Groundling		✓								+	+	+	+
9	<i>Acisoma panorpoides</i> (Rambur, 1842)	Asian Pintail		✓								+	+	+	+
10	<i>Orthetrum glaucum</i> (Brauer, 1865)	Asian Skimmer			✓										+
11	<i>Diplacodes trivialis</i> (Rambur, 1842)	Blue Percher		✓								+	+	+	+
12	<i>Potamarcha congener</i> (Rambur, 1842)	Blue Pursuer		✓								+	+		
13	<i>Trithemis pallidinervis</i> (Kirby, 1889)	Dancing Dropwing			✓										+
14	<i>Tholymis tillarga</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	Foggy-winged Twister		✓									+	+	
15	<i>Orthetrum sabina</i> (Drury, 1770)	Green Skimmer		✓								+	+	+	+
16	<i>Trithemis festiva</i> (Rambur, 1842)	Indigo Dropwing				✓									+
17	<i>Orthetrum luzonicum</i> (Brauer, 1868)	Marsh Skimmer			✓							+		+	+
18	<i>Crocothemis servilia</i> (Drury, 1770)	Oriental Scarlet		✓								+	+	+	+
19	<i>Neurothemis intermedia</i> (Rambur, 1842)	Paddyfield Parasol			✓							+	+	+	+
20	<i>Neurothemis tullia</i> (Drury, 1773)	Pied Parasol		✓								+	+	+	+
21	<i>Urothemis signata</i> (Rambur, 1842)	Scarlet Basker		✓								+	+	+	+
22	<i>Tramea limbata</i> (Desjardins, 1832)	Sociable Glider		✓								+			

23	<i>Brachydiplax sobrina</i> (Rambur, 1842)	Sombre Lieutenant		✓						+	+	+	+
24	<i>Rhodothemis rufa</i> (Rambur, 1842)	Spine-legged Redbolt			✓					+	+	+	+
25	<i>Rhyothemis variegata</i> (Linnaeus, 1763)	Variegated Flutterer		✓						+	+	+	+
26	<i>Pantala flavescens</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	Wandering Glider		✓							+	+	
Family: Platycnemididae													
27	<i>Onychargia atrocyana</i> (Selys, 1865)	Marsh Dancer				✓				+	+	+	+

National Conservation Status (The National Red List, 2012): LC = Least Concern, NT = Near Threatened, VU = Vulnerable, EN = Endangered, CR = Critically Endangered.

Table 4. Checklist of Butterflies in Kirala Kele Sanctuary (based on current study).

No	Scientific name	Common name	SL Endemism / Migrant	National Conservation Status					Transect				
				L C	N T	V U	E N	C R	T01	T02	T03	T04	
Family: Hesperiiidae													
1	<i>Ampitta dioscorides</i> (Hewitson, 1868)	Bush Hopper		✓						+	+	+	+
2	<i>Iambrix salsala</i> (Moore, 1866)	Chestnut Bob		✓						+	+	+	+
3	<i>Hasora chromus</i> (Cramer, 1780)	Common Banded Awl		✓							+		
4	<i>Taractrocera maevius</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	Common Grass Dart		✓						+	+	+	+
5	<i>Pelopidas conjuncta</i> (Herrich- Schäffer, 1869)	Conjoined Swift				✓				+		+	
6	<i>Telicota bambusae</i> (Moore, 1878)	Dark Palm Dart				✓						+	
7	<i>Suastus gremius</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	Oriental Palm Bob		✓									+
8	<i>Pelopidas mathias</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	Small Branded Swift			✓					+	+	+	+

9	<i>Potanthus confucius</i> (Felder, 1862)	Tropic Dart		✓						+	+	+	+
10	<i>Cephrenes trichopepla</i> (Westwood, 1851)	Yellow Palm Dart		✓						+	+	+	
Family: Lycaenidae													
11	<i>Discolampa ethion ethion</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Banded Blue Pierrot		✓						+			
12	<i>Jamides celeno</i> (Cramer, 1775)	Common Cerulean		✓							+	+	+
13	<i>Acytolepis puspa</i> (Horsfield, 1828)	Common Hedge Blue		✓						+	+		+
14	<i>Prosotas nora</i> (Felder, 1860)	Common Line Blue		✓						+		+	+
15	<i>Castalius rosimon</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Common Pierrot		✓						+			
16	<i>Jamides bochus</i> (Stoll, 1782)	Dark Cerulean		✓								+	
17	<i>Zizeeria karsandra</i> (Moore, 1865)	Dark Grass Blue		✓							+		
18	<i>Catochrysops strabo</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	Forget-Me-Not		✓								+	+
19	<i>Everes lacturnus</i> (Godart, 1824)	Indian Cupid		✓						+	+		
20	<i>Arhopala amantes</i> (Hewitson, 1862)	Large Oakblue		✓							+		
21	<i>Zizina otis</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	Lesser Grass Blue		✓						+	+	+	
22	<i>Jamides alecto</i> (Felder, 1860)	Metallic Cerulean		✓								+	+
23	<i>Jamides lacteata</i> (de Nicéville, 1895)	Sri Lankan Milky Cerulean					✓					+	
24	<i>Nacaduba hermus</i> (Felder, 1860)	Pale Four Lineblue			✓								+
25	<i>Lampides boeticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Pea Blue		✓									+
26	<i>Chilades pandava</i> (Horsfield, 1829)	Plains Cupid		✓							+	+	+
27	<i>Zizula hylax</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Tiny Grass Blue		✓						+	+	+	
Family: Nymphalidae													
28	<i>Ariadne ariadne</i> (Linnaeus, 1763)	Angled Castor		✓						+			

29	<i>Ideopsis similis</i> (Linnaeus, 1764)	Blue Glassy Tiger				✓				+	+	+	+
30	<i>Tirumala limniace</i> (Cramer, 1775)	Blue Tiger		✓						+		+	
31	<i>Mycalesis perseus</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Bush Brown		✓									+
32	<i>Junonia iphita</i> (Cramer, 1779)	Chocolate Soldier		✓						+			
33	<i>Mycalesis perseus</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Common Bush Brown		✓									+
34	<i>Ariadne merione</i> (Cramer, 1777)	Common Castor		✓						+			
35	<i>Euploea core</i> (Cramer, 1779)	Common Crow		✓						+	+	+	+
36	<i>Phalanta phalantha</i> (Drury, 1773)	Common Leopard		✓							+		
37	<i>Neptis hylas</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Common Sailor		✓						+	+	+	+
38	<i>Melanitis phedima</i> (Cramer, 1780)	Dark Evening Brown			✓								+
39	<i>Parantica aglea</i> (Stoll, 1782)	Glassy Tiger		✓						+	+	+	+
40	<i>Hypolimnas bolina</i> (Linnaeus, 1756)	Great Eggfly		✓									+
41	<i>Junonia atlites</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Grey Pansy		✓						+	+	+	+
42	<i>Euploea klugii</i> (Moore, 1888)	Brown King Crow		✓								+	
43	<i>Euploea phaenareta</i> (Schaller, 1758)	King Crow		✓									+
44	<i>Junonia lemonias</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Lemon Pansy		✓						+	+	+	+
45	<i>Orsotriaena medus</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Medus Brown		✓						+			+
46	<i>Junonia almana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Peacock Pansy		✓							+	+	
47	<i>Danaus chrysippus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Plain Tiger		✓						+	+	+	+
48	<i>Acraea violae</i> (Fabricius, 1807)	Tawny Coster		✓						+	+	+	+
49	<i>Ypthima ceylonica</i> (Hewitson, 1864)	White Four-ring		✓						+	+	+	+

Family: Papilionidae												
50	<i>Papilio polytes</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Common Mormon	✓						+	+		+
51	<i>Pachliopta aristolochiae</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Common Rose	✓								+	
52	<i>Pachliopta hector</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Crimson Rose	✓						+			
53	<i>Graphium agamemnon</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Tailed Jay	✓						+	+	+	+
Family: Pieridae												
54	<i>Eurema hecabe</i> (Linnaeus, 1764)	Common Grass Yellow	✓						+	+	+	+
55	<i>Delias eucharis</i> (Drury, 1773)	Common Jezebel	✓						+	+	+	+
56	<i>Catopsilia pomona</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Lemon Emigrant	✓						+	+	+	
57	<i>Catopsilia pyranthe</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Mottled Emigrant	✓						+		+	+
58	<i>Leptosia nina</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	Psyche	✓						+	+	+	

National Conservation Status (The National Red List, 2012): LC = Least Concern, NT = Near Threatened, VU = Vulnerable, EN = Endangered, CR = Critically Endangered.

Figure 2. Species discovery curve for each taxonomic group.

Figure 3. Percentage composition of Birds families resulting from the transect survey

Figure 4. Percentage composition of Odonate families resulting from the transect survey.

Figure 5. Percentage composition of Butterfly families resulting from the transect survey.

3. 2. Diversity indices for selected fauna groups

The respective calculated Shannon- Wiener diversity (H'), species evenness (E), and Simpson's diversity ($1/D$) values for each transect and each faunal group are listed in Table 5. T01 received the highest scores (1.85 and 1.99) H' value for butterflies and odonates respectively, while T02 shows the highest value H' for birds (3.42). The lowest H' value for butterflies (1.46) and odonates (1.21) shows T03, while T04 received the lowest H' score for birds (1.57).

Table 5. Calculated Biological indices for each taxa group for each transect.

Taxa Group	Transect	Shannon- Wiener diversity (H')	Species Evenness (E)	Simpson's Diversity ($1/D$)
Bird				
	T01	3.27	0.27	0.95
	T02	3.42	0.27	0.96
	T03	3.16	0.26	0.93
	T04	1.57	0.15	0.52

Odonate				
	T01	1.99	0.30	0.80
	T02	1.97	0.28	0.77
	T03	1.21	0.19	0.47
	T04	1.61	0.28	0.67
Butterfly				
	T01	1.85	0.43	0.83
	T02	1.61	0.50	0.80
	T03	1.46	0.46	0.74
	T04	1.79	0.47	0.83

According to the scores, the 1/D value for butterflies (0.83) was recorded in T04 while T02 for birds (0.96) and T01 for odonates (0.80) were scored the highest values respectively. In contrast, T03 scored the least for butterflies (0.74) and odonates (0.47).

According to the results, for the birds (0.52) least 1/D shows in T04. The highest evenness for the butterfly group is shown in T02 (0.50) while both T01 and T02 show the same score for birds (0.27). T01 received a 1/D value of 0.30 for odonates which is the highest among the transects while it received the lowest value for E for butterflies (0.43). T04 and T03 received the lowest E scores for birds (0.15) and odonates (0.19) respectively.

4. DISCUSSION

During this study, 20% out of 522 bird species present in Sri Lanka were encountered, belonging to almost half of the country's taxonomic families The National Red List (2021). The last inventory of the Kirala Kele area has been, 204 avian species according to the eBird (2021) online platform (Wijeweera 2022). The lower number of species observed in the current study could likely be due to the use of permanent transects during whole the study as the eBird provides a checklist of species in the whole Kirala Kele wetland and Adjacent areas. Transect 02 received the highest diversity of birds, which consists of paddy-water catchment areas offering a mix of terrestrial and aquatic resources. In contrast, the T04 woodland-water-holding ecosystem had the lowest bird diversity. This might be because more food resources are available in the T02. The migrant species recorded were spread across the transects, but the availability of water bodies, and marsh areas in T01 and T02 likely made these areas more attractive for migratory birds during the winter migratory season.

Present study results are in line with previous studies conducted in different parts of the world, where the family Libellulidae is the most widely spread family among odonates (Harisha et al. 2017; Wijesooriya et al. 2022). Nine odonata zones have been recognized in Sri Lanka

according to their distribution and the study area is located in the dry odonate zone of Sri Lanka which means the area has a low distribution of odonates compared to the other regions of the country. The highest diversity of odonates was observed in T01, which has a marshy ecosystem with a canal. This is an expected observation since odonates are highly dependent on freshwater ecosystems to maintain their life cycle. The presence of open and running water and dense aquatic vegetation likely provides ideal conditions for odonates to reproduce, feed, and pursue shelter. In comparison, T03, with its mixed riparian and cropland ecosystem, had significantly lower odonate diversity, potentially due to anthropogenic activities in the habitat structure and the lower availability of odonate-friendly micro-habitat types.

From the 247 of total recorded butterfly species in Sri Lanka (Van der Poorten & Van der Poorten, 2016) and 58 species (23.48%) were recorded during the study. The butterfly diversity was relatively well distributed among the selected transects, with T01 showing comparatively higher levels of diversity. However, T02 reported higher evenness for butterflies (0.50) suggesting that the mixed habitat types in this transect support a more balanced butterfly community. Butterflies are dependent on both nectar sources and host plants, and T02 offers a variety of both, likely supporting species across multiple life stages. (Karunaratna et al. 2011) states that the modern agricultural practices have replaced indigenous vegetation types and butterfly species diversity is significantly lower in such areas than in their natural habitats. This is probably due to the destruction of natural habitats and the extensive use of insecticides and other agrochemicals for agricultural purposes attached to such natural habitats.

Even though this semi-urban area is close to the Matara urban area and holds fairly rich biodiversity as expressed in the results, it is facing threats that include garbage dumping, habitat destruction for agricultural purposes by local people, and invasion of exotic flora and fauna (De Silva Benthota et al. 2015) including *Acacia* spp., *Salvinia molesta*, Water Hyacinth *Eichhornia crassipes*, *Hypostomus Plecostomus* (Tank Cleaner), *Trachemys scripta* (Red-eared Turtle), and *Lantana camera*. Further a review of the distribution of the birds, butterflies, and odonates faunal groups of the area based on the results of this study as a baseline study may provide a holistic insight into habitat distractions, climate change impacts, and the need for a complete study on life cycles of these species.

Moreover training, awareness and educating the local communities, farmers, visitors, and students from schools to universities to prevent pollution, overexploitation of resources, and fragmentation of existing wetland habitats in the area is a timely requirement. As this area employs agricultural activities to a greater extent, it should also be coupled with best agriculture practices to ensure sustainability among local communities and the environment.

5. CONCLUSION

The findings illustrate how ecosystem diversity within the Kirala Kele sanctuary contributes to species richness and diversity. Further checklists of all three selected faunal groups in the sanctuary presented here could be used as a baseline for future updates and studies in the area. The presence of marshy wetlands, riparian zones, and woodland ecosystems allows us to concord between wildlife and livelihoods. The heterogeneity of habitats within the sanctuary is crucial in maintaining the biodiversity of the region and conservation efforts should focus on protecting all the ecosystem types and livelihoods to ensure the long-term sustainability of this region.

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